

Supplementary Figure 1: Assay conditions to analyze immune responses between primary human CD4⁺ T cells and B-LCL cells using conventional and imaging flow cytometry

a Gating strategy to identify single interacting T-B-LCL synapses using the IDEAS software of the imaging flow cytometer.

b FACS histograms showing the surface-expression levels of MHCII (HLA-DR), CD80 and CD86 of primary CD19⁺ B cells from PBMCs and B-LCL cells.

c Quantification (MFI) of MHCII, CD80 and CD86 surface expression on primary CD4⁺ T cells, CD19⁺ B cells and monocytes from PBMCs and B-LCL cells. Data are from five donors in three independent experiments. The B-LCL cell line was analyzed in triplicates.

d Pre-testing of assay conditions using conventional FACS. Primary memory CD4⁺ T cells isolated from PBMCs of healthy donors were stimulated with B-LCL cells in the presence of different concentrations of SEA (0.1-100 ng/mL) or left untreated (-SEA). Frequencies of P-CD3ζ⁺, TNF-α⁺ and CD69⁺ CD4⁺ T cells were determined at various time points. The small FACS histograms in the bar graphs show the expression levels of the three markers by comparing the highest concentration of SEA (100 ng/mL) with the untreated control (-SEA) after 60 min. The data shown represents one experiment using T cells from three different donors.

e Percentage of single T-B-LCL synapses and P-CD3ζ⁺ CD4⁺ T cells measured by imaging flow cytometry between two different SEA concentrations (10 and 100 ng/mL) after 45 and 120 min. Data represents two donors.

a

b

w/ & w/o SEA	Experimental condition	Name referred in text	Donors											
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
	B-LCL + CD4 ⁺ T cell	-SEA or No Ab	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	B-LCL + CD4 ⁺ T cell + SEA	+SEA	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

c

control and activators	B-LCL + CD4 ⁺ T cell + [Condition]	Name referred in text	Donors										
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
			Ctrl-TCB					✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
B-LCL + CD4 ⁺ T cell + CD19-TCB	CD19-TCB					✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
B-LCL + CD4 ⁺ T cell + CD20-TCB	CD20-TCB					✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

d

control and inhibitors	B-LCL + CD4 ⁺ T cell + [Condition]	Name referred in text	Donors											
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
	B-LCL + CD4 ⁺ T cell + SEA + Isotype	Isotype	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			
	B-LCL + CD4 ⁺ T cell + SEA + Teplizumab	Teplizumab	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			

e

Interaction Type	Donors											Total		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11			
Singlets	Single B-LCL	127	125	74	68	101	51	41	48					635
	T cell w/o signaling	147	153	47	70	109	53	43	43					665
	T cell w/ signaling	64	124	64	67	42	47	41	46					495
Doublets	T cell w/ small B-LCL	80	182	41	72	109	55	44	44					627
	B-LCL & T cell in one layer	85	101	69	68	95	31	41	43					533
	Synapse w/o signaling	38	114	43	81	102	33	38	44					493
	Synapse w/ signaling	61	161	58	147	28	101	47	58					661
Multiplet	No cell-cell interaction	86	120	75	80	75	87	32	64					601
	Multi-synapse	45	164	14	66	74	52	79	47					511

Supplementary Figure 2. Donors and experiments information

- a** List of the donors, their age, gender and experiment numbers which are used in this study.
- b** List of experiments and donors with and without SEA.
- c** List of experiments and donors with TCBs and their control.
- d** List of experiments and donors with Teplizumab and isotype control
- e** Number of labeled by expert data per donor